

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildirimler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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Gendered Asymmetries in Terms of Address in Moroccan Arabic

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Abstract

In the Moroccan sociolinguistic context, terms of address in dialectal Arabic constitute essential discursive markers in the construction of interpersonal relationships. Their use, far from being neutral, reveals complex social dynamics, particularly in terms of gender. The study of gendered asymmetries in these forms of address is part of a sociopragmatic approach, attentive to issues of power, politeness, and social recognition. This field of analysis allows us to better understand how language contributes to the reproduction or challenge of gendered social norms. The central theme of this research lies in identifying the linguistic mechanisms that differentiate speakers according to their gender, both in the production and reception of terms of address. These asymmetries reflect implicit representations of the feminine and the masculine, often associated with stereotypes or symbolic hierarchies. Some expressions tend to make the feminine invisible or relegate it to affective or subordinate registers, while other, more marginal expressions open up spaces of discursive resistance.

The methodology adopted is based on the analysis of a corpus of authentic interactions collected in various informal contexts (family, public spaces, means of transportation), supplemented by a sociolinguistic questionnaire. The sociopragmatic approach allows for the intersection of linguistic, interactional, and social dimensions, taking into account variables such as gender, age, status, and interactional context.

The results reveal gendered asymmetries in terms of address, ranging from valorization to stigmatization. They show that speakers adjust their linguistic choices according to social expectations and interpersonal relationships, and can also use them to assert an identity or challenge power relations.

Keywords: Moroccan Arabic, gender, verbal interaction, social representation, interpersonal relationships.

Introduction

International To address someone, linguistic expressions are used which are referred to in the scientific literature by a range of terminological labels, Depending on each author's theoretical assumptions and field of inquiry, such as vocatives, referential terms, address forms (I will adopt the term "address form" throughout this study hereafter referred to as AF). They take on several morphological forms spanning most parts of speech including personal pronouns, common nouns, and proper nouns They can group several elements in their composition. They are endowed with remarkable semantic diversity in meaning and interpretation.

This terminological, lexical and semantic range is reflected in the choice of AF within the language practices of Moroccan speakers, which proves to be a complex psychosociocultural exercise. Addressing a girl will not be the same as addressing a boy, especially as the girl's age may be a determining factor. Moreover, we need to see how this form of address will be perceived? and for what communicative intention it is employed? This outline of questions and along with other relevant factors shows us how the critical importance of analyzing AF, especially when it comes to a context with a varied sociolinguistic fabric such as Morocco. Studies dealing with AF in the Moroccan context remain scarce, however the literature review in the French context has significantly contributed to this field, in particular with Catherine Kerbrat-Orecchioni through her studies on verbal interactions [6].

In this study, which is concerned with the important role that AF play in the language practices of Moroccans, we plan to analyse their uses, as well as their potential effects on perception and, above all, the impact they have on interpersonal relationships.

This analysis sheds light on the sociolinguistic dynamics of Moroccan language practices beyond social relations. It highlights the particularity of the phenomenon of address in these relationships across various socio-cultural contexts. In other words, it focuses on the usual and atypical forms of AF in correlation with social factors such as gender and their impact on interpersonal and social relationships.

Conceptual and Sociolinguistic Foundations

It seems interesting to me to proceed with a terminological framework aimed at clarifying the notions of appellative, designative, and term of address.

1.« Appellatives »

The Dictionary of Linguistics defines appellatives as "terms of language used in direct communication to address an interlocutor by naming him or her or by indicating the social relations that the speaker establishes with him or her. Appellatives are proper nouns, kinship terms or specific names" (Dubois, et al., 2012).

Perret reserves appellatives for the designation of human beings in language; "appellatives are defined by both function and form. When a lexical term is used in discourse to refer to a person, it becomes an appellative" (Perret, 1970, p. 112).

- Usual appellatives: these are terms used to designate a person, such as proper nouns, common nouns, personal pronouns, titles, certain relationship terms, kinship terms, etc.
- Terms used metaphorically to designate a human being: certain terms that do not literally designate a person may be used conventionally within the linguistic community to address someone, such as my treasure or my great. These terms can be considered as usual appellatives because of their conventional use in certain circumstances.
- Non-usual terms: certain metaphorical terms or adjectives used to designate a person, such as "*mon chiendent*" (my weed) or "*mon aboulique*" (my abutment) (Perret, 1970, 113).

At this stage, a few defining features emerge: the appellative refers to any term in the language that fulfils the grammatical function of naming human addressees exclusively in direct communication.

On the other hand, in the linguistic literature of the 1970s and 1980s, the term "appellative" is used in a confused manner with "vocative," which refers to inflectional languages. According to Dubois (2012), "the grammatical function performed by appellatives in direct communication is called the appellative function. This interpellation of the interlocutor by the speaker is translated by the vocative in case languages" (Lehman, 2010). This terminological clarification shows that there is a metonymic relationship between the function and the very nature of these phrases, since the term "vocative" refers to the vocative function. The latter can often be identified by intonation in verbal interactions.

2. « Designatives »

While appellatives refer to the notion of appellation, "designatives" are concerned with reference and mention, i.e. talking about others to third parties. In her research on "designatives" and terms of address, D. Lagorgette notes that designatives are "nominal syntagms for naming and designating characters They are the key elements in the construction of reference" [8]. She also notes their different linguistic uses in narrative and discourse, as well as their various grammatical functions, since they can be subjects and object complements in the sentence.

3. Terms of address between « appellatives » and « designative »

The notion of the term of address refers to verbal interaction in its dialogical aspect, where at least two participants interact, often using terms of address in order to define each other. Kerbrat-Orecchioni defines it as "a set of expressions available to the speaker to designate the addressee" (Lagorgette, 2002). In the French language, she distinguishes two types of term of address: pronominal forms of address that have a deictic value, in particular with "je" and "tu (vous)", and nominal forms of address.

The distribution of pronominal forms of address varies from one language to another. French and German have two personal pronouns, "tu", which is used for direct address and characterises a familiar relationship, and vous, which is used as a polite term for indirect address, while Arabic and English have only one, for direct address. However, Portuguese, Romanian, and Hindi have three pronouns; in addition to the one expressing a familiar relationship, there are two polite pronouns in two distinct levels. Other languages, such as Japanese and Korean, may have five (Bernat, 2015), (Traverso, 2007).

Nominal forms are defined as "noun phrases with a vocative function" (Kerbrat-Orecchioni, 1992), V. Traverso explicitly uses the term "appellative" to designate this type of term of address, tracing the same typology cited above by D. Perret.

As for the difference between "terms of address" and "designatives", D. Lagorgette discusses how they function: "designative noun groups referring to characters in the narrative find a referential relay in direct speech: terms of address. These two types of nominal group function in pairs, or dyads, and in addition, the negative family, relational and axiological AF are saturated clutches" (Lagorgette, 2000).

4. Apostrophe

The notion of "apostrophe", even before it is evoked in the field of rhetoric and figures of speech, refers to the oratorical device which consists in sharply and unexpectedly addressing a person present or absent, or even a personified thing. In grammatical terms, it refers to the word that represents the person or thing being addressed. As such, it is a form of language uttered in a specific discursive context, characterised by a distinctive tone. Once again, the importance of intonation as a criterion is clearly underlined, as is the vocative. The results of numerous studies show that the term apostrophe encompasses addresses to human beings, animate entities and inanimate objects.

Methodology

To carry out a scientific study, a conceptual and methodological choice must be made. The latter is part of a qualitative approach with the aim of achieving the preconceived objectives, in particular the search for significant crossovers between sociolinguistic variables such as gender, which is understood throughout this work as a social parameter categorising individuals according to their biological sex. In addition, the description of the use and interpretation of the linguistic forms fulfilling the function of address and appeal demonstrated by the speaking subjects is complicated in such a way that the phenomenon of address, except for the measurement of the lexical frequency rate, escapes any statistical aim.

The corpus

This study is based on a corpus consisting of voice recordings of random situations in the daily lives of Moroccans, which were made during our doctoral research in public spaces in three different cities, namely: Fez, Rabat and Temara, using a professional tape recorder. During the survey, we tried to adopt a participatory stance in the various verbal interactions we witnessed to obtain as much linguistic data as possible. In other cases, however, we were content to observe verbal productions directly, which enabled us to avoid the paradox of the observer. In addition, a questionnaire was a tool in its own right in our work; it was drawn up in two forms: electronic and empirical and was published in November 2023.

The population concerned by this research is chosen at random, in other words, any person frequenting public places who crosses our path will be considered as a (potential) subject of the survey.

It should be noted, however, that public places are known to be frequented by people of all ages, genders and social statuses.

As the data collected was in Moroccan Arabic, a language without a solid orthographic tradition, it was transcribed manually in the absence of reliable transcription software for spoken Arabic. In addition, the data obtained from the questionnaire will be coded and analysed using Excel software.

The questionnaire

The questionnaire administered consists of 25 questions, alternating between open and closed questions. It is divided into three parts:

The first deals with intrinsic and language indicators (age, gender, dialect spoken, social status, etc.).

- How does your father call your mother at home? in front of a group of people of the same sex? in front of a group of people of different sexes?
- In what context do you use the structure “wəld or bənt mother's first name” to call someone?
- How do you address a woman in the street? - How does your father call your mother at home? In front of a group of people of the same sex? in front of a group of people of a different sex?
- When you usually approach someone, what term of address do you use?

The third part is reserved for the interpersonal effects of the use of AF. E.g.

- How do you behave when someone calls you: “wəld (son) or bənt (daughter) + your mother's first name”?
- How do you behave when someone calls you: “wəld (son) or bənt (daughter) + your father's first name”?
- What is the social value of using the structure “wəld (son) or bənt (daughter) + mother's first name”? and comparing it with the structure “wəld (son) or bənt (daughter) + father's first name”?
- In what context do you use the expression “hbiba”?

The interviewees who responded to the questionnaire represent 45% of the female sex and 55% of the male sex, all spread across all age groups.

Results

The analysis of the data obtained from this research highlights the comparative approach according to the social parameter gender in its two intra-sexual or inter-sexual dimensions. Terms of address are an important part of the naming system in Moroccan Arabic; they are the focal point of every exchange and are characterised by a diversity of linguistic forms, ranging from the usual to the metaphorical. Moroccan men and women generally use the usual linguistic forms to designate or define a person, such as first names, titles, trade names, kinship terms, patronymics and affective terms, but they also use fictitious metaphorical expressions.

1. FICTITIOUS EXPRESSIONS OF KINSHIP AND RELIGIOUS REFERENCE

We note that over 80% of respondents use fictitious terms of kinship to refer to a man or woman: “*χūja*” (brother), “*χti*” (sister), “*lwālid*” (father), “*lwālida*” (mother). Almost 20% use religious terms of reference: “*Muhamed*”, “*lhāz*”, “*lhāz3a*”, “*chrif*”.

Table 1: Use of fictitious terms of address

	fictitious kinship term of address		religious reference terms of address	
	Man	Woman	Man	Woman
Man	79%	97%	21%	15%
Woman	70%	78%	30%	12%
Right Usage rate of metaphorical AF	80%		20%	

The recourse of Moroccan speakers, both men and women, to the abundant use of fictitious kinship terms [χūja], [χti], [lwālid], [lwālida], [wəldi], [bənti] in interpellation, illustrates the way in which each participant in the interaction positions himself in relation to his interlocutor in the contextual construction of the interpersonal relationship [15]. Thus, the choice of AF expresses the speaker's self-image and the place he wants to have with the interlocutor. An intentional effect is manifested by a certain interactional limit in accordance with societal values. The fictitious AF of kinship maintain a certain distance that is also equivalent to respect for the interlocutor (Lagorgette, 2000).

In the following interaction, a couple sitting in the café is joined by a young man:

a) - The young man: Salām Siham kidājra, biḫir, kolchi labāss?

(Hi Siham how are you, everything all right?)

- The girl ; ?hlān χūja Hicham, hamdūllāh biḫir, kanqddām lik χatibi Jalal

(Welcome my brother Hicham, thank God I am well, let me introduce you to my fiancé Jalal)

- The young man : ; ?hlān χūja, mabrūk flikūm χti Siham.

(Welcome my brother, congratulations my sister Siham)

The AF of fictional kinship in this situation (a) clearly confirms its distancing value, since the use of the girl's first name by the young man indicates a familiarity between the two participants in this verbal exchange, an old acquaintance, it is the "dimension of decisive knowledge" that motivates his choice (Perret, 1970). However, the girl's response, using the structure [χūja]+ first name, obliges him to stand back and keep his distance, a "social reduction" is required (Perret, 1970), something he clearly understands when he makes up for it in his turn to speak. In addition, the girl uses it to clear up any illusions or misunderstandings that might emerge in her fiancé's mind.

Furthermore, the increasing number of participants in this interaction affects their linguistic behaviour; if the young man and the girl had any kind of relationship before, it will be modified by the arrival of the third person (the fiancé). Thus, new rules are established (Searle, 1969); on the one hand, the young man will not call the girl by her usual first name in the presence of her fiancé. On the other hand, he refrains from calling the latter by his first name, and opts for a fictitious kinship FA.

b)- When the train arrives at the terminus, a young boy sitting away from his bag asks a traveller to take the bag away for him.

- firi, firi, s'āk

(My friend, my friend, the bag)

Faced with the recipient's indifference, the young man addresses another female traveller.

- Xti, llāh ḥafdʿak, hadāk sʿāk.

(My sister, may god protect you, that bag)

The lexico-semantic construction of the two formulations raises the question of cultural and linguistic value, which operated not only according to the gender of the interlocutor but also at the level of the speaker's linguistic behaviour. The change from FA [ʃjiri] to [Xti], as well as the care taken in formulating politeness through an invocation [llāh ḥafdʿak] towards the girl, marks the respect and social distance that must be established in intersex verbal exchanges. On the other hand, [ʃjiri] refers to the extreme familiarity, or even casualness, that develops between two people of the same sex. Its use in this situation is explained by the speaker's aim of bringing his addressee into his sphere of intimacy. However, the reaction of the traveller, whose intimacy has been violated, is to decline the request without responding favourably (Goffman, 1974). Consequently, faced with this multimodal interactive game, the young boy proceeds to self-repair (Kerbrat-Orecchioni, 2005), in his choice of lexicon and linguistic attitude.

2. THE SYSTEM OF ADDRESS IN THE FAMILY

In the familiar context, the results showed that the system of address between couples has changed considerably. The first name is now used more frequently to call the spouse, accounting for 75% of other linguistic forms of address. The AF [mūl eḏḏār] (house owner) and [mūlāt eḏḏār] (house owner) regain a prominent place in situations of naming the spouse in the presence of a same-gender or different-gender group. Affective forms such as [ḥbiba] (love), [rāzli lʃziz] (my dear man/husband) and [mrāti lʃziza] (my dear wife/wife), as well as the AF [abū] (father) or [ūm] (mother) + first name of the son or daughter, occupy a negligible place.

The choice of the appropriate AF changes from one situation to another depending on the speaker's intentions and the identity of the interlocutor. As already shown above, the proper name marks the relationship of familiarity and intimacy in direct address, in harmony with the conception of the modern family as open to societal change, thus replacing other forms, particularly those referring to tribal or paternal affiliation in traditional families. In conservative families, however, the formula [abū] or [ūm]+ the son's or daughter's first name is used.

The forms [mūl eḏḏār] and [mūlāt eḏḏār], reserved for designation in the absence of the referent, are antonomases that have an honorific value for the person designated as the king and queen of the house.

Table 2: Forms of TA and their frequency in the family context.

	Direct address			A group of the same gender			A group of a different gender		
	First name	ḥbiba - Rāzli lʃziz -	Mūl eḏḏār- Mūlāt eḏḏār	First name	ḥbiba - Rāzli lʃziz -	Mūl eḏḏār- Mūlāt eḏḏār	First name	ḥbiba - Rāzli lʃziz	Mūl eḏḏār- Mūlāt eḏḏār
Father	75%	10%	20%	30%	3%	72%	30%	3%	74%
Mother	75%	8%	27%	35%	5%	60%	32%	5%	63%

Men's reluctance to mention their wives' names in friendly discussions can be attributed to a number of psychosociological and cultural factors. In Moroccan society, there is a certain modesty or tradition of respect towards women, where their names are considered private and not meant to be shared with strangers or even close friends.

The linguistic taboo surrounding the names of women, whether wives, mothers or sisters, can be seen as a way of preserving their integrity and respectability. Not mentioning a wife's name can be interpreted as a mark of respect for her and for the private sphere of the family.

Moreover, in such a patriarchal society, there is a social hierarchy in which men are considered to have a higher status and their identity is often put forward. Thus, in friendly discussions, men may be more inclined to talk about themselves, their achievements or subjects that concern them directly, rather than mention their wives.

Finally, men may also avoid mentioning their wife's name out of concern for protecting their privacy and that of their family.

In summary, men's reluctance to mention their wives' names in friendly discussions may be due to a combination of traditional respect, preservation of privacy and social norms regarding gender roles and hierarchy in society.

3. "WƏLD / BƏNT + MOTHER'S OR FATHER'S FIRST NAME"

Regarding the use of the linguistic form "wəld or bənt + mother's first name", 52% of men said they had used it for reasons of humility in everyday verbal exchanges, while 56% of women said they had used it out of respect for the other person.

However, when answering the question about the use of the form "wəld or bənt + father's first name", the research results show that most women and men use it to express respect for the speaker or their fathers.

As regards the interpretation of the use of the structure "wəld or bənt + mother's or father's first name" in relation to socio-cultural values, most men felt that the use of the AF referring to the mother was devaluing and inappropriate compared with the other AF referring to the father. The majority of women, on the other hand, consider that both structures are appropriate and that there is no difference (Auger, Fracchiolla, Moïse, & Schultz-Romain, 2010).

4. METAPHORICAL AF.

It would be interesting to highlight an atypical use of linguistic forms that function as FA; this metaphorical use manifests itself in different contexts. Here are a few examples:

c)- In a walk, a man intentionally crushes another man's foot and continues on his way. Surprised by this gesture, the victim tries to call him

- wa simohamed, wa train

(Hey Mohamed, hey the train??)

d)- In an amusement park, some young people are playing with a ball, when someone perches it. Arrived next to a man in his thirties sitting on the bench

- ƣammi l kora.

(My uncle, the ball)

- moqataƣa, ƣamala...

(The district, the province/prefecture)

e)- A young man is hitchhiking when the driver of a city car stops.

-lblyayda 3afak centre

(The tribe/the village, please, the town centre)

In these three language situations, speakers use metaphorical AF for various communicative reasons. While in (c) and (d) the AF of religious reference simohamed (preceded by the vocative particle wa

denoting interpellation), or that of the fictional kinship *ʕammi* considered as conversation starters, did not actually fulfil their interpellation function, since the potential interlocutors pay no attention to the speakers' requests. Consequently, the speakers resort to other linguistic forms describing the behaviour or aptitude of the interlocutor: on the one hand, the train to illustrate the non-stop nature of the person being addressed. On the other hand, *moqataʕa* and *ʕamala* describe his static and motionless status. Concerning situation (e), the speaker's use of *lɓlayda*, which evokes the common geographical and tribal belonging of the partners in the interaction, is motivated by the need to find someone who will accept his request.

DISCUSSION

The forms of address used in the Moroccan linguistic community are closely linked not only to the system of interpersonal relations and roles established between the participants in the verbal interaction, but also to the socio-cultural values corresponding to the individual perception of each member of the community, man or woman (Kerbrat-Orecchioni, 1992) (Kerbrat-Orecchioni, 2005) (Traverso, 2007).

Understanding these differences in the use of forms of AF - namely proper nouns, the terms of fictive kinship “*χūja*”, “*χti*”, “*lwālid*”, “*lwālida*”, “*wəld*”, “*bənt*” or the patronymics “*wəld*” or “*bənt + mother's or father's first name*” - depends on the context in which the verbal exchanges take place.

Indeed, the AF of fictive kinship have a value of estrangement and distancing. On the other hand, proper nouns are indicators of familiarity and intimacy. Thus, the specific form “*mūl eḏḏār*”, “*mūlāt eḏḏār*” to designate respectively the husband and the wife refers to the noble status of this institution which is the family in the collective memory of Moroccans to such an extent that its members are honoured by this appellation.

As for the contrast between the use of “*wəld*” or “*bənt + the mother's or father's first name*”, this is no exception to the patriarchal system that prevailed in traditional Moroccan society, which means that any reference to the father, considered to be the head of the family, is valued. On the other hand, changes in society, especially with the reform of the family code and the emergence of single mothers, are frowned upon, leading to people being referred to by their mother's name, which places them in the negative category of fatherless children. This humiliating form of address is widespread among young people.

Conclusion

Our initial question was to describe the use of AF in the language practices of Moroccans and the effect it has on interpersonal and social relationships.

Any verbal exchange takes place within a framework set at the outset, which determines its conditions and the linguistic forms potentially employed, and consequently highlights the expression of the relationship, if not the relationship itself. As a result, context is a crucial factor in the choice of AF as an indicator of the opening of verbal exchange. In terms of production, the choice of the term of address depends not only on the speaker's intention, which is generally to address the second person, whether neutrally, metaphorically or fictitiously, with the aim of initiating a conversation, but also on the characteristics of the interlocutor, in particular the degree of proximity, identity, social appearance and gender. At the level of perception, this use can produce various interpersonal effects, such as valorisation, stigmatisation, respect, humiliation, etc. Moreover, it will be perceived as appropriate or inappropriate depending on the parameters of the socio-cultural context in which the interaction takes place. In reality, each lexical term used by a speaker in his discourse reflects a specific choice he makes in relation to the subject he is talking about. This choice goes beyond a simple selection from the lexical options available; it designates the subject of his discourse in a particular way, motivated by a specific reason, and therefore expresses his relationship with the subject of his discourse by modulating it. This aspect of language is as significant as its referential or semantic aspect. As far as AF in spoken Arabic

is concerned, as in any other language, it is the subject of a deliberate study of social and interpersonal relations. The reason why this study has excluded kinship terms is that they explicitly name the social relationship, whereas the other AF do not explicitly predicate this relationship; it is necessary to resort to the interpretation of the implied, so that the analysis of linguistic behaviour confirms the sociological analysis

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليّن أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

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